

DEBT MANAGEMENT OFFICE
NIGERIA**DOMESTIC DEBT DATA FOR THE 36 STATES OF THE FEDERATION AND THE FEDERAL CAPITAL
TERRITORY AS AT MARCH 31, 2020**
AMOUNT IN NAIRA

SN	STATE	DEBT STOCK (N)
1	ABIA	69,634,039,326.56
2	ADAMAWA	101,585,003,141.05
3	AKWA IBOM	240,030,073,468.00
4	ANAMBRA	33,917,442,019.21
5	BAUCHI	100,409,185,575.21
6	BAYELSA	154,951,999,955.49
7	BENUE	116,199,896,419.54
8	BORNO	83,386,455,106.94
9	CROSS-RIVER	165,919,327,215.69
10	DELTA	230,752,395,527.53
11	EBONYI	42,418,253,950.80
12	EDO	84,763,453,988.79
13	EKITI	77,879,220,526.63
14	ENUGU	62,981,314,822.66
15	GOMBE	82,509,992,299.90
16	IMO	163,995,242,446.03
17	JIGAWA	36,020,470,211.81
18	KADUNA	78,693,577,244.62
19	KANO	107,753,774,512.23
20	KATSINA	66,164,163,901.64
21	KEBBI	69,265,493,403.43
22	KOGI	128,917,613,295.97
23	KWARA	62,895,645,473.39
24	LAGOS	444,227,001,473.16
25	NASARAWA	60,991,643,229.42
26	NIGER	59,831,608,197.74
27	OGUN	143,530,694,475.07
28	ONDO	65,295,186,224.27
29	OSUN	137,309,082,945.63
30	OYO	100,593,874,570.63
31	PLATEAU	130,732,065,712.34
32	RIVERS	266,936,225,793.65
33	SOKOTO	47,745,884,844.80
34	TARABA	81,269,122,715.60
35	YOBE	29,294,892,028.57
36	ZAMFARA	70,841,492,738.26
37	FCT	106,800,716,861.16
Total		4,106,443,525,643.42

Important Notes

- 1 This Domestic Debt Data is generated from the signed-off submissions received from the 36 States of the Federation and the FCT
- 2 Domestic Debt Stock for Twenty Eight (28) States: Abia, Adamawa, Akwa Ibom, Bauchi, Bayelsa, Benue, Cross River, Delta, Ebonyi, Edo, Ekiti, Enugu, Gombe, Imo, Jigawa, Kaduna, Kogi, Kwara, Nasarawa, Niger, Ogun, Ondo, Osun, Oyo, Plateau, Sokoto, Taraba, Yobe and the FCT as at March 31, 2020.
- 3 Domestic Debt Stock Figures for 6 States: Anambra, Borno, Kano, Kebbi, Lagos and Zamfara were as at December 31, 2019
- 4 Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Katsina State were as at June 30, 2019
- 5 Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Rivers State were as at December 30, 2018